

Study of Reaction between 2-Amino-3-cyanopyrroles and Isothiocyanates. Synthesis of 4-Aminopyrrolo[2,3-*d*]-pyrimidine-2(3*H*)-thiones

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Reaction of 2-amino-3-cyanopyrroles (1) with various isothiocyanates (2) has been studied. Structures of the synthesised 4-aminopyrrolo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine 2(3*H*)-thiones (4) have been established and possibility of formation of pyrrolylthiourea (3) and 4-aminopyrrolo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines (5) was ruled out on the basis of elemental analysis, spectral data and chemical reaction.

NATURALLY occurring antibiotics tubercidin, toycamcin and sangivamycin have pyrrolo-[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine moiety¹. One of the important routes for the synthesis of pyrrolo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines is the annelation of pyrimidine ring onto existing 2-amino-3-cyanopyrroles². In continuation of our studies³ on such annelation, we present our results of reaction between 2-amino-3-cyanopyrroles (1) and various isothiocyanates (2) because of a little attention given to the synthesis of pyrrolo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines having thioxo functionality.

Reaction of 2-amino-3-cyanopyrroles (1) with various isothiocyanates (2) has been studied in different conditions and solvents like ethanol, diethyl ether, benzene, pyridine, sodium ethoxide and DMF-NaH mixture. Excellent yields (70–95%) were only obtained in pyridine. When 2-amino-3-cyanopyrroles (1b) substituted by aryl group at position-1 were reacted with isothiocyanates (2), the desired pyrrolopyrimidines could not be obtained under any of the conditions. Interestingly, the absence of aryl substituent at position-1 in 2-amino-3-cyanopyrrole (1a) enhanced the chances of the reaction with isothiocyanates.

Furthermore, the reaction (Scheme 1) could give either the uncyclised pyrrolylthiourea derivatives (3) or cyclised pyrrolopyrimidines (4 or 5). In none of the ir spectra, an absorption at 2 250 cm⁻¹ for cyano group was observed of pyrrolylthioureas (3). Structures 4 and 5 were then most likely with the same molecular formula. The ir spectra of the reaction products between 1a and isothiocyanates, exhibited absorptions at 3 450, 3 360 and 3 100 (γ NH₂, NH), 1 640 (δ NH₂), 1 550 and 1 380 (N–C=S) and 1 100–1 060 cm⁻¹ (C=S) (Table 1), which was supported by ¹H nmr spectra to arrive at the conclusion. The ¹H nmr spectrum, for example of 4a, exhibited signals at δ 5.1 (2H, s, NH₂), 1.3 (3H, s, CH₃) and 7.15–8.35 (11H, m, ArH) which suggested that the product could be with 4-amino functionality 4 and not 5. The structure was further established by chemical reaction.

1a: R=H 1b: R=Aryl
R₁=Phenyl, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-tolyl, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-anisyl, *n*-butyl, cyclohexyl

Scheme 1

Supposing 5 to be the correct structure, it should give 2-methylmercaptopyrrolo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines (6) when methylated with dimethyl sulphate in the NaOH, but several attempts to get the desired 6 failed, indicating the absence of available tautomeric proton for methylation. Ultimately it was confirmed that 4-aminopyrrolo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine-2(3*H*)-thiones

(4) is the correct structure which is in agreement with the reported work⁴. Compounds 4 are yellow crystalline solids, soluble in dioxane, DMF and DMSO but insoluble in water and alcohol.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer IR-180 and IR-397 spectrophotometers and ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Perkin-Elmer R 12B (60 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc using benzene-ethanol (8 : 2) on silica gel-G (1 mm) and spots were revealed by iodine. 2-Amino-3-cyanopyrroles were synthesised by Gewald reaction⁵.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4*

Compd. no.	R ₁	Yield %	M p. °C
4a	Phenyl	86	318-19
b	o-Tolyl	91	310-12
c	m-Tolyl	70	318-19
d	p-Tolyl	75	333-34
e	o-Methoxyphenyl	70	290-91
f	p-Methoxyphenyl	88	292-93
g	m-Chlorophenyl	79	287-88
h	n-Butyl	95	312-13
i	Cyclohexyl	74	309-10

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

4-Amino-3-substituted-5-methyl-6-phenyl-7H-pyrrolo[2,3-d]pyrimidine-2(3H)-thiones (4) : A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol), isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) and pyridine was refluxed in an oil-bath for 3-7 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and diluted with aqueous ethanol. The resulting solid was washed with aqueous ethanol, dried and crystallised from EtOH-DMF mixture (Table 1).

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References

1. Y. MIZUNO, M. IKEHARA, K. A. WATANABE, S. SUZAKI and T. ITOH, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 3329; K. V. RAO, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1963, **11**, 939; R. K. ROBINS and L. D. TOWNSEND, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 2102.
2. V. AMARNATH and R. MADHAV, *Synthesis*, 1974, **12**, 837.
3. C. G. DAVE, P. R. SHAH and S. P. UPADHYAYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 713; C. G. DAVE, P. R. SHAH, S. P. UPADHYAYA, T. P. GANDHI and R. P. PATEL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect B*, 1988, **27**, 778.
4. H. WAMHOFF and H. A. THIEMIG, *Chem. Ber.*, 1985, **118**, 4473; H. WAMHOFF and B. WEHLING, *Chem. Ber.*, 1976, **109**, 2983.
5. K. GEWALD and M. HENTSCHEL, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1976, **318**, 663; C. G. DAVE, P. R. SHAH and S. P. UPADHYAYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 713.